

Multimedia Integration on Students' Proficiency in Drafting Roof Plan

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ABSTRACT

This research study aimed to determine the effect of multimedia integration on the proficiency level of Grade 9 students in drafting roof plans. Employing a quasi-experimental method and utilizing a test questionnaire as a tool for gathering data from the respondents, the study evaluated the performance of 42 students who received either traditional instruction or multimedia-integrated instruction. The results of the study revealed a statistically significant difference between the two groups of students. The study results highlight the superiority of multimedia instruction over traditional instruction in terms of proficiency achieved by the students. While the traditional instruction group exhibited an approaching proficiency level of competency, the multimedia instruction group demonstrated an advanced level of proficiency. The latter group surpassed the core requirements of knowledge, skills, and understanding and could apply them with ease and flexibility to authentic performance tasks. The findings of this study provide strong evidence in support of the use of multimedia instruction as a tool for enhancing academic outcomes. The combination of texts with pictures and audio-video features enhances the learning experience of students, making it more engaging and interactive. The study emphasizes the importance of integrating multimedia instruction in the academic setting to enhance the performance of students. These findings underscore the importance of incorporating multimedia resources in teaching practices to enhance student's learning outcomes and promote their level of expertise.

Keywords: *multimedia integrated instruction, students' proficiency level, drafting roof plan*

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INTRODUCTION

The implementation of the K to 12 curriculum prepares students with the technical knowledge and skills requirements for various opportunities of the 21st century (Sanchez et al., 2020). One of these opportunities is the specialization of Technical Drafting. Technical Drafting is a specialization under Technical Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) track in the K to 12 curriculum and students are expected to create technical drawings as individual output to obtain the required competencies (Vito et al., 2019). One of these competencies is the Drafting Roof Plan, and multimedia can play a vital role in the acquisition of these competencies. As stated by Widayana et al., (2020) that interactive multimedia could direct students in understanding engineering drawing material and also practice drawing skills (psychomotor aspects) with the addition of audio-video or interactive animation. Furthermore, he concluded that the utilization of interactive multimedia in the Engineering Drawing course proved effective in improving the drawing skills of Mechanical Engineering students.

In education setting, Information and Communication Technology had been used as one of the instructional materials for optimizing the student's learning environment. Information and Communication Technology has become a vital part of the learning and teaching process and has had a considerable influence on the characteristics and functioning of education in most countries (Kim, 2022). Its integration into the course content is emphasized to increase the effectiveness of learning and acquisition of knowledge (Sun, X. et al., 2022). As stated by Shunkov et al., 2022 rapid advancements in multimedia technologies are significantly transforming educational practices worldwide. Respectively, in further research, it has been empirically demonstrated that technology integration quality positively impacts student learning outcomes (Fütterer et al., 2022; Consoli et al., 2023; Stegmann, 2020). Moreover, it enables interaction, reaction, and enthusiasm in the learning process (Stylianou et al., 2019).

Similarly, developing nations have explored different strategies including the use of multimedia technology (Abdulrahman, M.D. et al., 2020). There have been many studies that prove the use of multimedia in learning can overcome several problems in various disciplines or subjects (Budiarto et al., 2020). As revealed by (Shamir et al., 2019) they found that students were positively impacted on their academic performance and allow students to see visually from the subject matter. Additionally, a study conducted in the Philippines by Cruz et al. (2019) revealed that the use of multimedia can help the performance of students by doing their tasks easily and presenting creative projects, ideas, or presentations. Thus, multimedia can improve learning, and motivation and make them more independent and participative because the graphics are engaging and appealing to them (Akinoso, 2020; Yaftian, N., & Barghamadi, S. 2022; C. Matias, R., & Agapito Jr., B. 2022). Nevertheless, despite the great impact of this method in teaching and learning, there is a dearth of studies on the effect of multimedia integration on students' proficiency specifically in the field of Drafting Roof Plan in the Philippines.

Recent research has shown that incorporating multimedia into teaching can have a positive impact on learning outcomes. At Anahawan National High School, teachers have been utilizing this strategy by incorporating PowerPoint presentations, audio, images, and animations into their lessons, these teachers have been able to provide concrete examples that

help learners build their mental representation of the topic. Additionally, educational multimedia games have been used to enhance students' literacy skills and provide a fun and engaging way to complete learning activities such as reporting.

Nevertheless, despite having access to ICT equipment such as personal computers, laptops, internet connection, and television in the classroom, it has been observed that students' proficiency in drafting roof plan competency is low. According to the Least Learned Skill report from the previous academic year (2019-2020), students at Anahawan National High School faced difficulties when it came to drafting roof plans. Students failed to demonstrate an understanding of concepts and principles in the preparation of roof plan layouts and details. Moreover, some students are unable to prepare architectural roof plan layouts and details based on the job requirements such as indicating the dimension of the roof plan based on the floor plan and drawing framing details of the roof plan according to architectural drafting standards.

In addition, students exhibited disinterest and a lack of motivation during lessons, despite the incorporation of multimedia. Learners' focus in the lesson is on a short span only that makes ineffective integration of multimedia and contradicts the effectiveness of multimedia integration on students' performance. The statement above was supported by Bastow, (2023) that attention span of people has decreased over the years. Additionally, he claimed that another reason for the reduced attention span is how information is presented to students nowadays. As Rapanta et al., (2020) highlighted that without an interactive environment and strong teacher-student interaction, multimedia alone would not suffice. Thus, multimedia can be deduced from the studies that most of the tools are applied either as teaching or/and learning aids depending on the nature of the audience and teacher (Abdulrahman, M.D. et al., 2020).

This research is to determine the effect of multimedia integration on the students' proficiency in drafting roof plan. The study aims to provide concrete evidence and feedback in an area where there is a scarcity of information regarding the effectiveness of multimedia integration. The primary objective is to address concerns and doubts regarding the efficacy of multimedia integration in this competency by providing empirical evidence of its usefulness as a teaching strategy or method. By gathering actual data and proof, the study aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of multimedia integration, contributing to the body of literature and filling critical knowledge gaps.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of multimedia Integration on students' proficiency in drafting roof plan.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following question:

1. What is the students' proficiency level in drafting roof plan using the traditional instruction?
2. What is the students' proficiency level in drafting roof plan using the multi-media integrated instruction?
3. Is there a significant difference between the students' proficiency level in drafting roof plan using traditional and multi-media integrated instruction?

4. What output can be proposed based from the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a quantitative approach to gather numerical data, which was then analyzed to identify trends and averages. Utilizing quantitative approach allowed researchers to evaluate the effect of different teaching methods on the proficiency level of students. The Quantitative Quasi-experimental method was employed, which involves comparing groups of participants to determine the effect of multimedia (independent variable) on students' proficiency level (dependent variable).

According to Hassan (2023) quasi-experimental design is a research method that seeks to evaluate the causal relationships between variables, but without the full control over the independent variable(s) that is available in a true experimental design. In this design, the researcher used an existing group of participants that was not randomly assigned to the experimental and control groups. Instead, the groups were selected based on pre-existing characteristics or conditions, such as age, gender, or the presence of a certain medical condition (Hassan, 2023).

A comparison between the experimental group and the control group was conducted. The experimental group utilized multimedia in the teaching and learning process, while the control group used the traditional way of discussion and dialog in the teaching and learning process. Furthermore, since the variables were controlled, both groups were the same in terms of subject, academic level, teacher, and teaching location, and the two groups had undertaken evaluation.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

For this study, the researcher used the purposive sampling method as viewed most appropriate approach, since the researcher aimed to conduct an in-depth study on two selected grade 9 sections that the researcher specifically handled. According to Hassan (2023), purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique used in research to select individuals or groups of individuals that meet specific criteria relevant to the research question or objective. The primary reason for this sampling method was to identify samples that were well-suited for addressing research questions of the study.

The study involved 42 Grade 9 students currently enrolled in technical drafting as part of their Technology and Livelihood Education course at Anahawan National High School, located in Anahawan, Bato, Leyte. The participants were divided evenly into two classes, with 21 students in each group. The research considered various educational environments, including classroom and other suitable learning situations.

Anahawan National High School was selected as the ideal research site for multimedia instruction on Technical Drafting for Grade 9 students. This public secondary institution has one School Principal, 32 teachers, four non-teaching staff, and a total of 847 students. It is situated approximately 11 km from the Poblacion, and it took a maximum of eight minutes to

walk from the highway to the school. Furthermore, the school was selected as the location for the study as the researcher is currently teaching TLE 9 in this institution.

Research Instrument

In this study, the researchers will use questionnaires as the research instrument to carry out the objective and target of the study, the researcher used the questionnaire as the tool for gathering the data from the respondents to determine the effect of multimedia on students' proficiency in drafting roof plan.

The test questionnaire was adopted from Technology and Livelihood Education Module 3 titled "Drafting Architectural Layout Details" page 137 and Module 1 titled "Basic Types of Roofs" page 11. The module selected was developed by the Department of Education and has been carefully evaluated by the DepEd officials. Thus, reliability of these questionnaire is no doubt. Moreover, the students' scores were categorized based on DepEd Memorandum No. 158, S. 2011. Whereas: Beginning (74% and below); Developing (75%-79%); Approaching Proficiency (80%-84%); Proficient (85%-89%); Advanced (90% and above). Moreover, categorizing students' scores enabled the tracking of students' progress in attainment of standards, promote self-reflection and personal accountability for one's learning as stated in DepEd Memorandum No. 158, S. 2011. Furthermore, allowing to enhance the instructional materials being used. As Dufitumukiza, B., and Twizeyimana, E. (2023) stated, teaching and learning to become fruitful, adequate well-designed instructional materials emerges as crucial factor.

The questionnaire used for the evaluation was used to measure the students' proficiency after exposure to multimedia instruction and traditional instruction. The questionnaire consisted of 30 items consisting of the Three sub-competencies as reflected in page 49-52. The questionnaire included 10 items of multiple choice, 10 items of labelling the roof framing and 10 items of Drawing of the roof plan which were rated through rubrics.

Data Gathering and Analysis

After obtaining all the necessary consent and assent letters, the researcher delivered the lesson using multimedia instruction for Class A and a traditional mode of instruction for Class B. The multimedia such PowerPoint Presentation, pictures, animation, and text were utilized in Class A as part of the multimedia instruction. Class activities such as discussion and evaluation administered using the PowerPoint presentation, Microsoft Word, and Paint application. Whereas Manila Paper, Chalk and Board were utilized in Class B as part of traditional instruction.

Subsequently, to determine the effectiveness of multimedia instruction in boosting students' proficiency level, a detailed plan was implemented. This plan includes a evaluation that was administered after the delivery of lesson using multimedia approach for Class A and a traditional approach in Class B. Furthermore, the posttest also comprised of questions to assess the students' knowledge and understanding of the subject matter. The evaluation scores undergone descriptive analysis, including calculating the mean score of the class. This analysis

enabled the teacher to evaluate the students' proficiency level following the integration of multimedia instruction.

All the data collected from the respondents were gathered to be analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software program. Furthermore, to measure the proficiency level of the students in drafting roof plan in the using traditional and multimedia instruction, mean score was categorized as follows:

Mean Score	Proficiency Level	Description
Less than 22.2 (74% and below)	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/ or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.
22.5-23.7 (75%-79%)	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understanding but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
24-25.5 (80%-84%)	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/ or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
25.5-26.7 (85%-89%)	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
27> (90% and above)	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.

Additionally, to assess whether multimedia used leads to any difference between the control and experimental groups, a t-test for independent samples with a significance value of 0.05 was employed. This statistical test facilitated a comparison between the two groups and enabled an examination of any noteworthy differences in their performance. By utilizing these statistical procedures, the study endeavored to assess the influence of multimedia instruction on students' proficiency and to establish the existence of statistically significant effects.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Distribution of Data on Students' Proficiency Level in Drafting Roof Plan Using the Traditional Instruction

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	Performance Level
Traditional Instruction	21	24.98	1.18	Approaching Proficiency

Legend: <22.2 Beginning, 22.5-23.7 Developing, 24-25.5 Approaching Proficiency, 25.5- 26.7 Proficient, 27> Advanced

Descriptive statistics on the Proficiency Level on the Traditional group was utilized and presented in Table 1. The Table elucidates the mean scores, standard deviations, and performance levels of the students who received traditional instruction. The data show that the students who were taught through traditional instruction obtained an average class score of 24.98, with a standard deviation of 1.18. Based on this score, it can be inferred that the student's proficiency level in the competency of Drafting Roof Plan, taught through traditional instruction, is positioned at the Approaching Proficiency level. This means that the student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understanding of the competency and with little support from the teacher or with some assistance from peers. Additionally, in the distribution of respondents' scores, it was noted that only two out of 21 respondents achieved the advanced level, while three fell within the developing level. These contributed to their performance level, which fell within the approaching proficiency level (Appendix G).

Furthermore, it was observed that the students who were taught through traditional method encountered difficulties while applying accurate measurements required in drafting the roof plan with a mean of 7.98, which was the lowest mean among the three test types (Appendix G). Among the 21 respondents, there were five who belong to Developing level which means that the students possess only minimum knowledge and skills and understanding of the drafting roof plan, thus they need help throughout the performance of the tasks. This implies that the students had difficulty in applying the steps in drafting roof plan, specifically in applying accuracy and proportion in drafting roof plan and need further assistance from the teacher.

Based on the result, it can be inferred that the learners have exhibited to approaching level of proficiency in the competency using the traditional method and requires further development and refinement to achieve a higher level of mastery. This result highlights the need for targeted interventions and instructional strategies to help students progress beyond the Approaching Proficiency level and achieve a higher level of proficiency. This implies that the traditional teaching method is effective in the teaching-learning process, however, there is a need for further improvement or intervention in the instruction to help students achieve advanced proficiency levels. This finding is supported by Lauc et al., (2020) who state that traditional learning is similarly interesting, instructive and funny, however, multimedia presentations are more interesting and instructive than funny. The students learned better and appeared more intrigued and positive responses compared to those who learned without multimedia instructional messages. As stated by Workie (2020) the instructional methods adopted by technical teachers greatly affect the learning of technical drawing.

Table 2. Distribution of Data on Students' Proficiency Level in Drafting Roof Plan Using the Multimedia Integrated Instruction

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	Performance Level
Multimedia Instruction	21	27.98	2.06	Advanced

Legend: <22.2 *Beginning*, 22.5-23.7 *Developing*, 24-25.5 *Approaching Proficiency*, 25.5-26.7 *Proficient*, 27> *Advanced*

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the scores of the Multimedia group in the Draft Roof Plan domain, displaying the mean scores, standard deviations, and performance levels of the students who received multimedia-integrated instruction. Based on the data presented in Table 2, it is observed that the students who received multimedia-integrated instruction scored impressively high, with a mean score of 27.98 (S.D. 2.06). This indicates that the students who were taught through multimedia-integrated instruction displayed advanced proficiency in drafting Roof Plan. This means that the students go beyond the core conditions in terms of knowledge, skills and understanding of the competency, allowing them to transfer it automatically through authentic performance tasks.

Additionally, it was also noted that while applying accurate measurements required in drafting the roof plan, students faced certain difficulties. The mean score in the Drafting roof plan test was 9.07, which was the lowest among the three types of tests (Appendix G). Furthermore, the distribution of respondents' scores showed that only two out of 21 students fell in the developing level, while 18 out of 21 respondents fell in the advanced level. This contributed to their performance level falling to the advanced level (Appendix G). It implies that even though some students only achieved a developing level in test three (Appendix G), their scores were surpassed by those students who achieved an Advance level. This indicates that the majority of the students who were taught using multimedia were able to accurately acquire and apply the necessary steps for drafting a roof plan.

Based on the outcomes, the inference can be yielded that the integration of multimedia resources such as videos, graphics, and animations in the course enhanced the students' comprehension of the concepts and enabled them to apply them more effectively. Like the result study of Widayana et al., (2020) that the utilization of interactive multimedia in the Engineering Drawing course proved effective in improving the drawing skills of Mechanical Engineering students. Furthermore, additional audio and video contents made the multimedia design looked more attractive, thus increasing students' motivation and independence of learning.

Table 3. Significant Difference Between the Students' Proficiency Level Using Traditional and Multimedia Integrated Instruction

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	Df	Independent Sample T-Test		Significance
					tComputed	p-value	
Traditional Instruction	21	24.98	1.18	40	5.769	.000	

Multimedia Instruction	21	27.98	2.06	Significant
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An independent sample t-test was employed to determine the proficiency level of the students on Draft Roof Plan competency after exposure to traditional instruction and multimedia instruction. This method is effective in finding the relative impact of each instructional approach, allowing for a deeper understanding of which approach produced more statistically significant outcomes. Through a comparison of evaluation scores within each approach, the independent sample t-test allows for a precise assessment on the significant difference of the instruction utilized in both the Traditional and Multimedia groups.

Based from the data on Table 3, there is a significant difference between the scores of the students who were exposed to traditional instruction and multimedia-integrated instruction. As shown in Table 3, the computed t-value, which is a measure used to determine statistical significance, was found to be equal to 5.769. This value is greater than the p-value, which was .000, indicating that the difference between the two sets of scores is significant. This means that if the t-value is greater than the p-value there is a statistically significant between the two instructional methods.

The significant results means that the students who received multimedia-integrated instruction exhibited advanced proficiency in drafting the Roof Plan compared to their peers who received traditional instruction, as the multimedia group reached the Advance proficiency level while the traditional group only reach the approaching proficiency level. This suggests that the utilization of multimedia in instruction can positively improve students' understanding and performance.

Like the study of Malhotra, R. and Verma, N. (2020) entitled “An Impact of Using Multimedia Presentations on Engineering Education” concluded that the utilization of Multimedia Presentations in engineering education makes the teaching-learning environment better as well as attractive. It helps in increasing the creativity in both the teacher and the student as it provides much space to exercise one's skills to be it acquired or owned.

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

This research determined the effect of multimedia integration on the proficiency level of Grade 9 students at Anahawan National High School in Anahawan, Bato, Leyte. The study was tailored to 42 grade 9 students who are currently enrolled in the school year 2023-2024. The researcher conducted a competency examination in the second quarter of the school year 2023-2024, assessing both multimedia instruction methods in Class A and traditional instruction methods in Class B based on the TLE 9 – Drafting roof plan competency.

The researcher employed a quasi-experimental method in the research study and carried out its objective and target using a test questionnaire as the tool for gathering the data from the respondents. The questionnaire was used for evaluation and to measure the student's

proficiency after being exposed to multimedia instruction and traditional instruction. Students' performance or score was categorized into different proficiency levels as required in DepEd Memorandum No. 158, S. 2011. Whereas: Beginning (74% and below); Developing (75%-79%); Approaching Proficiency (80%-84%); Proficient (85%-89%); and Advanced (90% and above). Furthermore, a t-test independent sample with a significant value of 0.05 was employed to statistically test the comparison and examine the noteworthy differences in the performance between the traditional and multimedia groups.

The findings of the conducted study show a significant difference between the proficiency level of the students in drafting Roof Plan using traditional instruction and multimedia integrated instruction. Students who were taught using traditional instruction have demonstrated to approaching level of proficiency in the competency Drafting Roof plan. This means that they have developed fundamental knowledge, skills, and a core understanding of the competency, however, they required slight guidance from the teacher or assistance from peers. This shows that traditional teaching methods are effective in the teaching-learning process, but further improvement or intervention is necessary to help students achieve advanced proficiency levels. Conversely, students who were taught using multimedia instruction scored impressively high, which fell in the Advanced level. This means that these students go beyond the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understanding of the competency, allowing them to transfer it automatically through authentic performance tasks. This implies that most of the students who were taught using multimedia were able to acquire and apply accurately the steps in drafting a roof plan.

Furthermore, Statistical analysis revealed that the computed t-value significantly exceeded the p-value. This means that if the t-value is greater than the p-value, there is a statistically significant difference between the two instructional methods. These findings suggest that the variance between the two sets of scores is statistically meaningful. The results of this study underscore that students who received multimedia-integrated instruction outperformed their peers who underwent traditional instruction in drafting the Roof Plan, displaying a more advanced level of expertise.

Conclusion

The present study offers an insightful analysis of the multimedia integration on students' proficiency level in drafting roof plan. The study results demonstrate that multimedia instruction is more effective than traditional instruction in terms of achieving higher proficiency levels among students. It can be concluded that integrating multimedia in drafting lessons can be an excellent tool for enhancing students' proficiency. The combination of texts, pictures, and audio-video features enhances the learning experience of students, making it more engaging and interactive. In general, the multimedia integration approach is undoubtedly significant to the teaching-learning process. However, its integration requires the teachers' expertise in relating the use of multimedia in teaching and learning activities to achieve the competency desired. Furthermore, it is also important to note that learners' involvement in the use of multimedia is crucial for its effectiveness as they are the end-users.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn from the study conducted, the following recommendation:

- a. Encourage school administration and teachers to improve the technological infrastructure of the school, which will provide opportunities for multimedia use. Teachers should be encouraged to use multimedia tools in all subjects to maximize the learning potential in their classrooms.
- b. Provide students with relevant engagement in multimedia and ICT equipment, which can enhance their learning experience.
- c. Adopt the proposed action plan for multimedia instruction to ensure that students receive the best possible education. Initiate a multimedia plan that aims to provide students with an interactive and personalized learning experience. Incorporate a variety of multimedia tools, including audio, video, graphics, and animation, all of which are expected to enhance the learning journey.
- d. Further studies may be conducted to understand the effect of combining AI and multimedia in addressing the technical drafting competencies.

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